

Synthesis of 1,6-Bis(2-Imino-3-Allyl-4-Substituted Thiazole-N²yl) Hexane, 1,6-Bis(2-Imino-3-Allyl-4-Thiazolidinone-N²yl) Hexane and 1,6-Bis(1N-Allyl-Thiohydantoin-N³yl) Hexane.

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Condensation of N,N' allyl hexamethylene bis-thiourea(I) with α -haloketones and chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate from II and III respectively. I when reacted with chloroacetic acid in presence of pyridine gave 1,6-bis (1N-allyl thiohydantoin-N³yl) hexane (IV).

THIAZOLES, thiazolidinones and thiohydantoins find various applications as antifungal, local anaesthetics, amoebacidal and herbicidal agents.¹⁻⁴ In continuation to our work on the synthesis of bis-thiazolidinones⁵ and screening them for their antifungal and antibacterial properties, the present communication deals with the synthesis of some new bis thiazoles (II), bis-thiazolidinone (III) and bis-thiohydantoin (IV). 1,6-Diaminohexane on treatment with allyl isothiocyanate gave N, N'-allyl hexamethylene bis-thiourea (I), which when condensed with α -haloketones furnished, 1,6-bis-(2-imino-3 allyl-4-substituted-thiazole-N²yl) hexane hydrohalides (II). I on reaction with chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate, gave 1,6-bis (2-imino-3 allyl-4-thiazolidinone-N²yl) hexane (III), whereas in presence of pyridine yielded 1,6-bis (1N-allyl-thiohydantoin-N³yl) hexane (IV) respectively.

The structures of compounds II, III, and IV are in conformity with the I. R. spectra (*vide* experimental). The lack of absorption in the region 1670-1700 cm⁻¹ in compound II (R=C₆H₅) suggests the formation of a thiazole ring. III when condensed with *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde gave the arylidene derivative. The antifungal and antibacterial properties of the compounds are in progress.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Infra-red spectra were taken in Nujol mull.

N, N'-Allyl hexamethylene bis-thiourea (I): 1, 6-Diaminohexane (2.32g, 0.02 mole) was dissolved in dry benzene (20ml) and allyl isothiocyanate (4.0 g, 0.04 mole) was added drop wise and cooling under ice-cold water. A milky suspension appeared. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for about one and a half hour. The solid thus obtained on cooling was filtered, washed repeatedly with ether and crystallized from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 100-102°. Yield, 5.0 g (79.5%). (Found: S, 20.1; N, 17.25. Calcd. for C₁₄H₂₆N₄S₂: S, 20.38; N, 17.83%). ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) 1165, 1190, (C=S), 1585, 1655 (C=C, C=N), 3080 (C-H stretching), 3250 (-NH).

1, 6-Bis-(2-imino-3-allyl-4-phenyl thiazole-N²yl) hexane (II, R=C₆H₅, X=Br): A mixture of I (1.04g, 0.003 mole), phenacyl bromide (1.33 g, 0.006 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (15ml) was heated under reflux on a steam bath for 4 hours. The solid separated on cooling was filtered, washed with a little ether and finally crystallised from ethanol-ether, m.p. 262-65°

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(decomp.). Yield 1.5 g(67.0%) (Found : S,9.15 : N,7.88. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{26}N_4S_2Br_2$: S,9.47 : N,8.28%). ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 700, 755 (monosubstituted benzene ring), 1590, 1650 (C=C, C=N), 3160 ($\overset{+}{N}H$).

II(R = -C₆H₄ - C₆H₄, X = Br) was prepared from I(1.04 g, 0.003 mole), *p*-phenyl phenacyl bromide (1.84 g, 0.005 mole) and anhydrous ethanol (20ml) following the above procedure, m.p. 240° (ethanol). Yield 1.4g, (50%). (Found : S,7.38 ; N,6.64. Calcd. for $C_{42}H_{44}N_4S_2Br_2$: S,7.73 ; N,6.76%). ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 700, 770, 840 (monosubstituted and 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring), 1590, 1605 (C=C, C=N), 3180 ($\overset{+}{N}H$). II(R = *p*-Br - C₆H₄, X = Br) m.p. 248° (ethanol-ether). Yield 1.3 g (47%) (Found : S,7.32 ; N,6.27. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{26}N_4S_2Br_4$: S,7.67 ; N,6.71%). II (R = 3,4(HO)₂C₆H₃, X = Cl) 260°, (58%) (Found : S,10.09. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{26}N_4S_2Cl_2O_2$: S,10.34%).

I, 6-Bis(2-imino-3 allyl-4-thiazolidinone-N²yl) hexane(III). A mixture of I (3.14 g, 0.01 mole), monochloroacetic acid (2.0 g, 0.02 mole), anhydrous sodium acetate (2.0 g) in anhydrous ethanol (30ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 7-8 hours. The solvent was concentrated and then poured over ice-water. A gummy solid appeared which solidified on keeping overnight. m.p. 68-70° (aqueous ethanol). Yield 2.2g (56%). (Found : S,15.97, N,13.88. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{26}N_4S_2O_2$: S,16.25 ; N,14.21%). ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1641, 1610 (C=C, C=N), 1715 (C=O), 3101 (C-H stretching). 5-*p*-Nitro benzylidene derivative, m.p. 172-75° (aqueous acetic acid). (Found : S,9.42. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{22}N_6S_2O_6$: S,9.69%).

I, 6-Bis(1*N*-allyl-thiohydantoin-N³yl) hexane(IV) : I(1.55, 0.005 mole), chloroacetic acid (1.0 g, 0.01

mole) and pyridine (6ml) were heated on a water bath for about 7-10 minutes. An exothermic reaction took place. The reaction mixture was cooled and anhydrous ethanol(15ml) was added and it was refluxed for about one and a half hour. On cooling, the solid thus obtained, was filtered, washed with a little alcohol and finally crystallized from ethanol in colourless flakes, m.p. 165° (decomp.). Yield 1.00 g(51%). (Found : S,16.33 ; N,14.15. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{26}N_4S_2O_2$: S,16.25 ; N,14.21%). ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1500 (C-N stretching), 1600, 1650(C=C, C=N), 1740 (C=O), 3040-3140 (C-H stretching).

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